

METHOD OF MAKING DRIED MELON

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726290>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

дыня, новые сорта
дынь, агротехнология,
влажность, сушка,

ABSTRACT

С целью изучения последних достижений учёных, ведущих исследования по данной тематике авторами был проведён обзор некоторых зарубежных статей, посвящённых переработке плодов дыни. В статье приводятся некоторые сведения о сушке дынь и технология получения сушеных продуктов. Приведены основные характеристики сортов дыни выращенные в Республике Каракалпакстане.

Melon is one of the main vegetable crops. It is not only a useful food when it is ripe, but also does not lose its flavor even after processing. Melons contain sugar compounds such as glucose, fructose and sucrose, as well as large amounts of fiber, hemicellulose, pectin and others. In addition to planting melon seeds, it is used to extract oil and peel as fodder for livestock.

In Uzbekistan, 15-20 thousand tons of melon seeds are used annually to produce melon seeds. As a result of processing melons in this quantity, we can get more than 1000 tons of dried melon. This allows farms to earn extra income.

To dry the melon in the sun, in a simple way, it is necessary to have a platform, table, knife, tray, rail, hemp thread and stainless steel wires. The perimeter of the drying area should be open, well-lit, and away from major roads. Melon drying is carried out on specially equipped hooks. To do this, the equipment is made of rails 6x6

cm in diameter with a height of 170 cm. On the opposite side of these rails are mounted triangular-width 1-meter trailers. The triangular-shaped trailers are installed at a distance of 2.5 meters and are again reinforced with rails. Wire or canvas is pulled at intervals of 35–40 cm, making 4–5 rows on both sides. In order to dry one ton of crop in a season (when dried 4 times), we will have to prepare equipment from 9 pieces of wood.

When drying melons, pay attention to the following:

- The drying area must always be clean.
- control the cleanliness of the table and sorts, if necessary, clean them with alkaline solution during production.
- Workers cut the melon into pieces, cut, wire and conduct instruction to comply with technical safety in all production processes.
- to see the possibility of protecting the rooms from pets and rodents, which

process the raw materials and store the dried finished product.

- Before drying the melon must be fully equipped with all the necessary tools and they must be in working order.

All varieties of ripe and unripe melons are suitable for melon peeling. But depending on the degree of density of the meat, it is advisable to choose a different method of cutting and drying it. We can dry the hard-boiled varieties "Ishi kizil", "Aq tuhum", "Kokshe", "Gulabi", "Toq sari" and others in simple ways in loops. The meat is cut during cutting and hanging of soft meat varieties "Bosvoldi", "Toshloqi", "Gurbek", so after cleaning they are cut into pieces, cut, spread and dry for 2-3 days, so ng we hang on the wires so that it dries well.

Depending on climatic conditions and the thickness of the melon pieces, the drying time lasts up to 6-12 days. Undamaged and undamaged melons are separated, they are washed or thoroughly cleaned with a damp cloth. Then divide into two equal parts and take the seeds. The cut pieces are cut into slices 3-4 cm thick, peeled and hung to dry in pairs. Melon flesh crunchy varieties (Kokshe, Ishi red) are pre-spread and dried due to the fact

that they are cut during slicing, and after softening, you can use the rails. The amount of dried finished product production varies in different varieties and is determined depending on the sugar content of the melon, the seeds, the thickness of the melon peel and the yield of the flesh.

Depending on the mechanical inspection of melon fruits, it is determined that their composition is different. Therefore, during the slicing of melons, different amounts of peanuts are obtained from each variety. 4.5-5.4% of melons are obtained from Koshe, Bosvoldi and Gurbek varieties. From other varieties 7.5-10.7% of the product is made. 11.7-15.2 tons of raw materials are needed to produce one ton of melons. In Uzbekistan, dried melons contain about 15.4-83.7 mg of vitamin C, a total sugar content of 38-75.7%, and dry matter 76-91.4%.

The readiness of the dried products is determined by the condition of the cut melon pieces. Melons should be pliable and should not leak when squeezed by hand, and the moisture content should not exceed 20%.

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